

Green Purchasing Implementation in Procurement Process of Kitchen's Goods in Improving Environmental Awareness at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran

Ni Luh Kadek Martha Andyani¹, Ni Nyoman Triyuni², Ni Putu Lianda Ayu Puspita³

^{1,2,3} Politeknik Negeri Bali

ABSTRACT: This study focuses on efforts to minimize the usage of single use materials by prioritizing the development of green products through the implementation of green purchasing by selecting suppliers and understanding the 3R impacts of reduce, reuse, and recycle in the procurement of kitchen's goods in improving environmental awareness at the Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran hotel. This study aims to analyse the implementation of green purchasing in the procurement process of kitchen's goods in improving environmental awareness at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. The research method used is descriptive qualitative using data collection through direct observation of the process of procuring kitchen's goods based on the implementation of green purchasing, which will have positive benefits in improving environmental awareness at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. Interviews were conducted with the assistant purchasing manager and purchasing agent of Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran, along with a documentation study method related to implementing green purchasing in the procurement process of kitchen's goods in improving environmental awareness at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. The results of this study indicate that Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran has not optimally implementing green purchasing because there are several obstacles, such as the price of goods with environmentally friendly packaging tends to be more expensive, difficult to obtain, and the limitations of suppliers who can provide kitchen's goods using environmentally friendly packaging. However, the purchasing section has gradually made an effort to replace items that use 100% conventional plastic with items that can be recycled.

KEYWORDS: environmental awareness, green purchasing, kitchen, procurement process, purchasing section, supplier.

INTRODUCTION

The tourism industry is a business sector that is growing very fast, but the existence of this industry causes environmental problems to become the main focus because the impacts are quite serious. In recent years, sustainable tourism gained interest in several countries and regions which has great tourism potential due to waste problems such as air pollution, land use, disturbance of the balance of nature and others. Sustainable tourism is a way to pass on to the next generation without destroying nature by providing for their needs in the future (Buyukipekci, 2014). The existence of the plastic waste will have a negative impact to the environment if It is not managed properly (Sabarno et al., 2021). This information is proven by the data which stated that in 2021 the volume of waste in Indonesia was recorded at 68.5 million tons and in 2022 it increased to 70 million tons. Furthermore, there is 24 percent or around 16 million tons of waste that is not managed. The increasement of environmental problems need the formation of environmental awareness in the society (*Direktorat Jenderal Pengelolaan Sampah, Limbah dan B3 (Ditjen PSLB3) Kementerian Lingkungan Hidup dan Kehutanan (KLHK)*). This is the reason why the companies must focus on their business activities to protect the environment as the main objective (Mkik et al., 2017).

At the moment, many tourists prefer to choose hotels that consistently implement environmentally friendly businesses (Rahmafritria, 2014). The environmentally friendly strategy is the way of the hotel to have purchase intention of various kind of green product using materials that do not damage the environment (Santoso & Fitriyani, 2016). Consumer behavior in choosing to use or buy green products is a form of tendency that is owned by consumers who have environmental awareness. This buying behavior is better known as green purchasing (Dwi et al., 2013). Green purchasing is the process of selecting and obtaining a product in the most effective way through a process of manufacturing and using of product can be recycled which will support environmental sustainability (Vazifehdoust et al., 2013). There are 2 dimensions of implementing green purchasing, there are supplier selection and 3R's procurement process. Supplier selection is a way of selecting suppliers based on criteria accordance with the standards set by the

company, while the 3R Procurement Process is a process of minimize plastic or paper (Pramesti et al., 2020). Implementation green purchasing also must be able to maintain good relations with suppliers. The role of suppliers in procurement of goods needs to be the main focus of the purchasing section because they have to pay attention to several criteria as a measuring tool for selecting the right supplier. So, it is very important for the tourism industry, especially the hospitality sector, to choose environmentally friendly products by implementing green purchasing in their company (Prasetyawan et al., 2018). One of the hotels that has been implementing green purchasing concept is Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran which is a 5-star hotel in the South Kuta area, Badung regency, Bali. This hotel offers a variety of facilities and accommodations such as 117 rooms divided into classic (15 rooms), deluxe (60 rooms), suites (34 rooms), penthouses (4 rooms), villas (4 rooms). Apart from providing accommodation, Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran also provides Food and Beverage outlets. There are several outlets such as Wala, Bamboo Chic, Smoqee, Pool bar, and Latitude 8. The revenue of Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran on January - December of 2022 obtained from several sources such as Room (29 billion), Food and Beverage (10 billion), Spa (500 million), Others (600 million). It can be seen that food and beverage is the second largest source of revenue after hotel rooms, which is around 10 billion of total revenue in 2022. The Food and Beverage Department plays an important role in a hotel because all the food and beverage service provided are the responsibility of this department, and the hotel's image will be influenced by the food and beverage service (Muliani et al., 2020).

In this case, Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran has not fully implemented green purchasing in procurement process of kitchen's goods. This hotel still uses single use materials such as plastic and paper because this material cannot be separated in production process especially for the kitchen. In addition, buying green products is expensive and most of supplier cannot provide the product that produced with expensive materials (Chan et al., 2018). Purchasing managers and agent purchasing should be able to use their knowledge and position to lead purchase of goods with an environmentally friendly concept by having good relationships with suppliers as a form of environmental awareness (Astawa et al., 2020). Purchasing section which is Assistant Purchasing Manager and Agent Purchasing at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran already have awareness in protect and preserving the environment by having knowledge, attitude and behavior that is shown in their activities to implementing buying environmentally friendly products gradually by replaced 100 percent pure kitchen's goods using conventional plastic into items that are easy to recycle especially for some packaging of kitchen's goods with the supplier that cooperate with Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran who offers environmentally friendly products for kitchen.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Green Purchasing

Green purchasing can be said as sustainable purchasing, which means that green purchasing is defined as the company's responsibility in purchasing a product by supporting environmental sustainability to achieve goals by minimizing packaging and by usage of recycle packaging also considering the relationship between product focus and the environment that has a significant impact (Jermstittiparsert et al., 2019). It can be concluded that green purchasing can be said as sustainable purchasing that is a process of purchasing an environmentally friendly product as one of the company's responsibilities in supporting environmental sustainability and also in the process of procuring goods must pay attention to reduce, reuse and recycle. There are 2 subs dimensions of green purchasing there are supplier selection and 3R's procurement process refer to Pramesti et al.,(2020). According to Chan et al., (2018), there are several things that needs to be considered when implementing green purchasing, that is the supporting and inhibiting factors such as (1) supporting factors: government policy, environmentally conscious consumer behaviour, and global issue (2) inhibiting factors: lack of proper guidelines in implementing green procurement, buying green products is expensive, the cost of the procedure for carrying out green procurement is quite expensive, procedures for implementation of green procurement are time consuming, there is a lot of admin burden to implement green purchasing, not enough qualified staff to handle green purchasing, sufficient funds or allocated budget is not available for the implementation of green purchasing, lack of commitment from top management within implementing green purchasing, lack of long-term observation, and low supplier commitment.

B. Procurement Process

Procurement process is an activity to get goods or services based on the needs and use of a company and also seen by considering the quality, quantity, delivery time, and affordable prices (Cahyo & Solikhin, 2015). It can be concluded that procurement process is an activity to obtaining a product, both goods or services based on the needs of the company, starting from the purchasing, receiving, until storing the goods by considering the quality, quantity, delivery time, and price of a product that is goods or services

to be purchased. There are 3 cycle of procurement process refer to Agung & Suparwi, (2022) such as (1) request of goods, (2) purchase of goods, (3) receive of goods. There are inhibiting factors in procurement process of goods that are usually faced by the company such as error from purchasing in making Purchase Order (PO), delay in approval from the general manager, and suppliers delivers goods not in accordance with PO Purchasing.

C. Kitchen

Kitchen is a location where food is made from processing to serving food which will be an attraction for guests who stay overnight or who just want to just enjoy a meal, of course making food will generate big profits for the hotel. Based on its duties, to make operational activities easier, the kitchen is divided into cold kitchen, hot kitchen and pastry kitchen (Hadinata & Adriyanto, 2020). In carrying out its operational tasks, kitchen certainly requires raw materials that can be obtained from the purchasing section, because all purchases of kitchen raw materials are the responsibility of the purchasing section. Purchasing must be able to pay attention to things in purchasing raw materials such as the number and quantity of goods, prices, and exact delivery times (Martina & Kurniawan, 2020). According to Sukma et al., (2020) there are types of food ingredients are classified such as (1) perishable food; perishable food is a type of food ingredient that is easily damaged, so a special storage method is needed for perishable food ingredients such as milk, meat, fish, seafood, fruits and vegetables. This type of food requires good cooling facilities, and must match according to the food quantity (2) semi perishable food; semi perishable food is a type of food ingredient that can be stored for a limited period of time at room temperature and has a longer endurance than perishable food. Types of semi perishable food such as onions, tubers, and bread. This type of food must be stored with low temperatures to maintain its quality (3) non-perishable food; non-perishable food is a type of food ingredient that can be stored for a long time at room temperature such as rice, noodles, flour, sugar, beans and other dry products. This type of food is non-perishable so it can be used longer than perishable and non-perishable types of food.

D. Environmental Awareness

Environmental awareness is an effort to understand environmental conditions that require saving and preservation (Mkik et al., 2017). Environmental Awareness is a curiosity for someone who has the knowledge, attitude and behavior to participate in understanding environmental issues by taking various actions to support environmental sustainability (Murniawaty et al., 2018). It can be concluded that environmental awareness is an effort of someone curiosity through their knowledge, attitude and behavior to understand several environmental issue and condition of the environment require preservation by taking various kind of environmentally friendly actions in order to support environmental sustainability. Refer to Junaedi & Fatmawati, (2016), there are 3 subs dimensions of environmental awareness there are environmental knowledge, environmental attitude, and environmental behaviour.

E. Hotel

Hotel is a business that provides various kind of services such as lodging services, food and beverage services as well as other supporting services that aim to gain profit in the form of money as the main benchmark. The services provided also take into account the profit and loss (Kholifatun et al., 2018). Minister of Tourism Regulation and Creative Economy of the Republic of Indonesia Number PN.53/HM.001/MPEK/2013 about Hotel Business Standards, namely hotels included in the business of providing accommodation. Meanwhile, the business of providing accommodation is a business that provides lodging services that can be complemented by other tourism services (Peraturan Menteri Pariwisata dan Ekonomi Kreatif, 2013).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The location of this research is conducted at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran, Bali, Indonesia. Data collection methods used in this research are observation, interview, and documentation. The data analysis technique used is descriptive qualitative analysis. Qualitative research is research that aims to understand the condition of a context by directing it to a detailed and in-depth description of the natural condition portrait of what actually happened in the field as it is. In this descriptive qualitative research, the information collected and processed must remain objective and analysed using appropriate techniques so that the information obtained is accurate. Refer to Miles & Huberman, (1994), states that the data flow consists of three activities namely, data reduction, data display, and conclusion/verification. Description of the analysis technique in this research is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Components of Data Analysis: Interactive Models

A. Collecting Data

Collecting data is done by observation, interviews with informants who were considered capable of understanding and providing accurate information and documentation related to the focus of the research problems. The sources of data used in this research are primary data and secondary data. In this research, primary data were obtained from research objects in the form of observations and direct interviews with assistant purchasing manager and agent purchasing at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. While, secondary data was obtained in this research is in the form of supplier invoice, purchase requisitions, market list, purchase orders and the others things that related with the implementation of green purchasing in procurement process of kitchen’s goods in improving environmental awareness at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran.

Table 1. The variable and indicator are presented in table below:

No	Variable	Indicator
1	Supplier Selection	1. Eco-labelling of product 2. Collaboration with supplier to use environmentally friendly packaging (degradable and harmless) 3. Assessment based on quality management system 4. Implementing a health, safety, and environment (HSE) system 5. Supplier ISO certification 6. Supplier eco-friendly research and development capability 7. Supplier internal management audit
2	3R’s Procurement Process	1. Reduce 2. Reuse 3. Recycle
3	Environmental Knowledge	1. Purchasing section have knowledge and understanding in recognizing environmental issues 2. Purchasing section have knowledge in recognizing environmentally friendly products 3. Purchasing section understand the impact or consequences of product purchases on environmental sustainability

4	Environmental Attitude	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The attitude of purchasing section to evaluate environmental performance on the impact caused by a product purchased2. The attitude of the purchasing section shown through efforts to minimize the negative impact of product purchases to the environment3. The attitude of purchasing section to have consistent concern in purchases environmentally friendly products
5	Environmental Behaviour	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Behaviour in reducing the use of plastic materials2. Behaviour in recycled waste management3. Behaviour in reusing the use of waste or sell the waste to the third parties

B. Data Reduction

Data reduction can be interpreted as a form of analysis to summarize, choose the main things, simplify, and focus on data and remove unnecessary things. Data reduction in this research is done by selecting, writing summaries or paraphrases, classification, and categorize. So, the reduced data will provide a clearer understanding for the writer and make it easier for the writer to carry out further data collection and is easier to find when searched.

C. Data Display

Data display in this research is done in the form of narrated interview summary, tables, charts, and relationships between categories so that make it easier to overview and interpretation of the data that has been obtained and its relationship to the focus of the research conducted.

D. Conclusion/Verifying

The last step of data analysis is conclusions. Conclusion in this research is done by making decisions based on the results of the analysis conducted from interviews with several informants with the aim of being able to refine the results of the analysis of this research.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Implementation of Green Purchasing in Procurement Process of Kitchen's Goods at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran

The implementation of green purchasing in procurement process of kitchen's goods at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran has not fulfil the whole of the indicators or criteria of green purchasing. This is shown from the procurement process of kitchen's goods which is carried out prioritizing the availability and suitability of goods with hotel operations needs without pay attention to overall impact of the purchases on environmental sustainability.

Supplier Selection: Refer to the SOP (standard operational procedure) of supplier selection at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran, it is selected based on price, brand, quality, and speed of delivery of goods to the hotel. First, in selecting suppliers is based on price orientation. Hotels will usually cooperate with suppliers who can provide payment systems for purchasing kitchen's goods by credit and who can provide negotiable prices. Usually, when the hotel makes a deal with a new supplier for the first time, some suppliers would ask for full advance payment. After repeat purchases, then the hotel will negotiate for a better payment system, which is credit system where the payment could be done within maximum one month after purchased the kitchen's goods. The next consideration on selecting the supplier is the brand of kitchen's goods, where usually the executive chef will suggest which brand should be purchase according to the request order that has been made. Then purchasing section will compare prices from several potential suppliers who sell the product brands at low prices but still pay attention to the quality of these kitchen's goods.

The selection of suppliers at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran is also looking on the quality and speed of delivery of goods. Product quality is related to kitchen's goods obtained or produced by the suppliers. Before dealing into agreements with suppliers, the purchasing section have to check the quality of kitchen's goods, especially for perishable food, and suppliers will provide product samples. Then the purchasing section will try to use kitchen's goods for 1 month, and when the trial period of using goods has consistently have good quality for 1 month, it will continue for the next month. After the quality of the goods have met the requirement based on the hotel SOP, then the collaboration is processed by making an agreement contract between the hotel and the supplier. Supplier selection is also based on supplier delivery speed because usually when the kitchen requires some urgent kitchen's

goods, the purchasing section have to order the kitchen's goods to the suppliers as soon as possible. It is necessary to work with suppliers who has flexible delivery time where the delivery sometimes will be out of their operational schedule.

Eco-labelling of product; In supplier selection, purchasing section does not require the products offered by suppliers to have eco labelling. In the implementation, products that have eco labelling are products that are prioritized to be served only for the guests. Because the cost is quite expensive. There are several suppliers that already include eco labelling on their products, but this is not applied to all suppliers who cooperate with Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. The selection of suppliers does not prioritize eco-labelling of products, but only based on the supplier's ability to deliver goods, credit payment systems, best quality, affordable price, fast delivery and of course fulfilling hotel requirements in procurement process of the goods. In addition, there are no policies or hotel operational standards written in the contract agreement that require the selection of suppliers based on eco labelling product. Some suppliers who have implemented eco-labelling of products are Yumico and PT. Micro Greens Indonesia. Yumico is one of the suppliers that cooperated with Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. Yumico offers a variety of quality food and beverage packaging at competitive prices. Of course, the packaging that provide is environmentally friendly and safe for health. This packaging is one of the products needed by the kitchen at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. Several packages from Yumico already contain eco labelling for example eco-kraft labels, recycle labels, biodegradable labels and others that makes by environmentally friendly material and methods. While, PT. Micro Greens Indonesia is local supplier and one of the suppliers that cooperated with Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran which offers healthy food products as garnishes needed by the kitchen at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. PT. Micro Greens Indonesia is a local business that cultivates high quality microgreens and also offers various types of young vegetable seeds and herbs that can be consumed through a planting process without pesticides, 100 percent organic and safe for health. This product is also packaged in environmentally friendly packaging and the packaging contains a recycle label which can be recycled because it is made from degradable materials.

Collaboration with supplier to use environmentally friendly packaging (degradable and harmless); Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran has been cooperated with suppliers to minimize the use of plastic by using environmentally friendly packaging. However, in reality not all of the suppliers can use and providing environmentally friendly packaging in procurement process of kitchen's goods to the Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. One of the reasons is because of the costs are quite expensive compared with conventional plastic products and the purchasing section cannot providing it in large quantities. In addition, there is no written agreement in the cooperation contract between the supplier and the hotel with the main orientation towards the environment by using environmentally friendly packaging, so that the supplier also has no obligations that must be carried out in procurement process of kitchen's goods at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran.

Assessment based on quality management system; Assessment of kitchen's goods is based on quality management. By checking the quality of the kitchen's goods used, the purchasing section must be able to select the highest quality od kitchen's goods from many potential suppliers offering kitchen's goods of the same type needed at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. Before deal the cooperation agreement that made with the supplier, the supplier will provide samples before using the item. The sampling will also be re-checked for feasibility, especially for perishable products such as meat, vegetables, fruits, fish, meat, seafood and so on. These products will be ensured good, safe, and guaranteed quality during the trial period. After that, then the purchasing section establish an agreement to use the goods that have been selected and ensure that the quality is guaranteed from the supplier that has been selected and has successfully passed the trial period.

Implementing a health, safety, and environment (HSE) system; All of kitchen's goods purchased through suppliers are guaranteed from health, safety, and environment system. This implementation has been written in the purchase contract between the supplier and the hotel. The agreement written in the contract contains all of kitchen's goods that are ensured to be safe and guaranteed from health, safety, and environment system until all of these goods are received by the hotel. Kitchen's goods received must be considered from the health aspect, these kitchen's goods must be ensured that they are safe for consumption or use by humans and do not have an effect on human health, then kitchen's goods are also ensured from a safety aspect starting from ensuring goods through a safe production process without must exploit resources excessively, and also ensure that in the process of sending kitchen's goods safely there are no kitchen's goods that are damaged and guaranteed quality to the hotel. The selection of kitchen items must also pay attention to environmental aspects, ensuring that as much as possible to avoid buying kitchen items that can damage the environment.

Supplier ISO certification; Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran has been collaborated with several suppliers that are certified ISO. Suppliers ISO Certification can be interpreted as various suppliers who provide goods through production processes using machines, and their production activities are guaranteed by a quality management system that is safe and does not have a negative impact on the environment. Types of ISO certification also vary depending on the type of production activity carried out by a company. However, it is still not fully implemented, because there are a lot of local suppliers have been chosen by Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran to become partners who are able to meet all kitchen needs. This ISO certification is not as the main orientation in selecting the supplier at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. One of the suppliers that has ISO certification is Yumico. Yumico is a supplier that provides kitchen's goods packaging that is environmentally friendly that produced using machines and all of the goods are guaranteed from the production process not to pollute the environment. This is proven by ISO22000 certification which can be seen in (Appendix 8). ISO22000 certification is a quality management security standard for a company that is directly or indirectly involved in the field of food production.

Supplier eco-friendly research and development capability; Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran have not fully developed environmentally friendly suppliers in providing various needs for kitchen's goods. Currently, the main orientation in supplier selection is price, brand, quality and speed of the delivery process. However, the hotel has awareness to conduct research on several suppliers that offer environmentally friendly products but in reality, supplier that offer environmentally friendly products is very limited because most of them can't sell goods that have highest price also difficult to obtained and lack of buyer's interest. Some kitchen's goods already use products that are environmentally friendly but not optimal in their implementation. Environmentally friendly products are only prioritized during certain events such as banquets, weddings, meetings or other events and environmentally friendly products are more focused or specifically given to guests

Supplier internal management audit; Purchasing section usually conducts audits by visiting the suppliers to evaluate the production process of goods needed by the kitchen is safe and hygienic. This activity is not done regularly due to the limited time and human resources in the purchasing section. However, the purchasing section has made a commitment to do this audit consistently twice a month and will start from May 9th, 2023. The process of this visit is purchasing section will ask the suppliers to make a visit first and make an appointment with the suppliers. Then, purchasing section will come to the place of supplier's production process also inform to the suppliers for making schedule to visit consistently twice a month.

3r's procurement process: Purchasing section make an effort to reduce the waste generated in procurement process of kitchen's goods at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran by ordering kitchen's goods using an electronic system so as to minimize the use of paper. The process of ordering kitchen's goods is starting from kitchen side submit the requisition form and market lists to purchasing section, then purchasing section will proceed the purchase to the supplier based on the purchase order documents that been submitted through the system. Purchasing section also uses products that can be refilled to reduce waste generated in procurement process. An example is using glass mineral water bottles that can be refilled to reduce the plastic waste generated at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran Initially, these bottles will be purchased from suppliers who provide them, then the glass bottles will be given to suppliers to be refilled. Certainly, it will be more environmentally friendly because the glass bottles can be used repeatedly. And these bottles are only prioritized to be served to guests, usually at banquets, weddings. meetings or events held at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. Purchasing section at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran uses the blank side of waste paper to reuse for making documents such as purchase orders, with the provision that the paper does not contain confidential data. Purchasing section at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran is also trying to use container and cardboard that can be used multiple times in procurement process of kitchen's goods such as fruits, vegetables and some canned food by collaborated with several suppliers that have initiative to provide and used container or cardboard in procurement process of kitchen's goods at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran selecting the organic waste that can recycled as a compost which can fertilize the plants around Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. This activity is usually carried out directly by the gardener who collects organic waste. Because, Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran has many kinds of plants. Some kitchen's goods packaging from several suppliers already contains an eco-labelling of product such as eco-kraft label, recycle label, which means that the packaging made with degradable packaging that can be recycled. However, a few of the many kitchen's goods that still use single use materials in procurement process at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran.

B. Implementation of Green Purchasing in Improving Environmental Awareness at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran

Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran's staffs are fully aware on the concept of green purchasing at the hotel. However, the implementation itself has not met the whole indicators and criteria of green purchasing yet. It is shown that the staffs have been trying to minimize the use of single-use materials, such as already minimized the use of conventional plastics which are replaced gradually with materials that can be recycled.

Environmental Knowledge: Purchasing section have the knowledge on environmental issues related to the procurement process of kitchen's goods in various ways. Purchasing section do the morning briefing every day and, on this briefing, the leaders usually share some information regarding the impact of the product to the environment. This section also joins some mandatory training and workshop which held by the Marriot International management where the topic is about sustainability, related to the process of buying products, procurement process and environmental impact. By joining this kind of training and workshop, the purchasing section could improve their knowledge about the environmental impact of the product, hence they will be more selective in the procurement process.

Purchasing section recognizing environmentally friendly products by looking at the eco labelling of products such as recycle label on the packaging of kitchen's goods. Besides, executive chef will inform the purchasing section on what kind of goods should be purchased based on his requirements. The goods requirement given by the executive chef usually in accordance with the criteria of environmentally friendly products. Other than that, purchasing section get the knowledge of environmentally friendly products from the hotel's suppliers. The suppliers usually inform the purchasing staff about the materials contained in the products to ensure these kitchen's goods use degradable materials and can be recycled.

Purchasing section understand the impact or consequences arising from buying kitchen's goods based on knowledge or education from the user (kitchen). In this case, the role of the kitchen section in providing information related to the use of kitchen's goods at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran is very useful for the purchasing section in buying kitchen's goods. Because, all purchasing decisions are in the kitchen section. Therefore, it can be concluded that the purchasing section will understand the impact and consequences of buying a product from the user. If the user still uses single use materials products, the consequences will be difficult to decipher, and will have negative impact for environmental sustainability. If the user already has the knowledge and awareness to use products made from degradable materials, so that can be easier to recycle, it means that the user already has an awareness of the environment. In addition, not all kitchen's goods can use environmentally friendly materials because the costs are quite expensive. Besides that, purchasing section also understands the impact and consequences of purchasing products of the environment from several Marriot International management trainings, such as training entitled "responsible sourcing" in program Serve 360, The benefits of this training to understanding and gaining knowledge of the purchasing section regarding environmentally friendly products that are safe to use from the right supplier and to know the impact of the product purchases to the environment.

Environmental Attitude: Purchasing section will evaluate the performance of a product based on the user (kitchen). So, the purchasing section will evaluate product purchases periodically to find out the risks found when buying these products. This risk will be a comparison, whether the product can still be used or not. And the purchasing section will coordinate with the user. Adjust quality, price, and impact to the environment. This is also contained in the provisions of Marriot International management regarding various purchase risks that have been distributed to several hotels under Marriot International management. Purchasing section in buying kitchen's goods will coordinate with users to evaluate purchasing activities that have risk to the environment, and assess whether the product is still feasible or not to be used.

Purchasing section strongly supports the existence of green products to minimize negative impacts to the environment. The purchasing section has replaced 100 percent pure kitchen's goods using conventional plastic into items that are easy to recycle. Minimum, the kitchen's goods such as thin wall use Polypropylene (PP) plastic with code 5, where this plastic is easier to recycle and safer to use than conventional plastic. In addition, the remaining used oil from the processing of kitchen food ingredients will also be sold to vendors who have been registered to processing the oil, not for sale and purchase. Because the oil contains harmful ingredients for human health and the environment.

Purchasing section has been quite consistent in buying kitchen's goods, but they still constrained in using green products 100 percent. It is because many suppliers cannot provide the needs for environmentally friendly kitchen's goods because difficult to obtain and the costs are a quite expensive. However, several products gradually using environmentally friendly materials. So, purchasing section must be cooperate with several suppliers to educate suppliers to be able in focusing the implementation of

environmentally friendly practices by prioritizing the existence and development of green products without harm natural resources such as animals and plants to take the parts needed to meet human needs.

Environmental Behaviour: This initiative is not fully compliance, because in the hotel operation side there was still using plastic for cover and Styrofoam as well. But this hotel committed to reduce single use materials and replace with degradable materials gradually step by step. Because, not all kitchen's goods can be replaced directly with environmentally friendly materials, some goods using environmentally friendly packaging still difficult to obtain, because limited suppliers are able to provide environmentally friendly materials, besides that the costs will also tend to be more expensive than other products using conventional plastic. Several goods or items other than kitchen's goods such as room amenities have also slowly been replaced with degradable and environmentally friendly materials. So, it will be easier to recycle. Habits that have been carried out by the purchasing section in handling procurement of goods are generally carried out to be able to reduce single use materials, usually the purchasing section has attempted to slowly replace 100 percent of kitchen's goods from conventional plastic to items that can be decomposed, at least from materials that use plastic with code number 5 namely Polypropylene (PP) which is safe to use, heat resistant and can be used repeatedly.

Purchasing section have reusing the blank side of paper as purchase orders, choosing products that can be refilled such as mineral glass water so that the glass bottle of mineral water can be reused, use multifunctional container in procurement process of kitchen's goods or cardboard that can be used repeatedly and for the solid waste such as plastic bottles, cardboard, tray egg carton, cans, and others will be sold to third parties that is the representative owner and the hauling waste conducted on every Sunday at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran.

Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran has awareness to protect and preserving the environment by separating solid waste included separating glass waste, organic waste, and paper waste to make it easier to recycle this waste which will be managed by third parties that is PT. Jimbaran Lestari. Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran has a contract with PT. Jimbaran Lestari on solid waste hauling. Every month PT. Jimbaran Lestari will send a report regarding solid waste of the percentage of materials that can be decomposed and leaves residue or not. PT. Jimbaran Lestari will help Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran to managed solid waste included paper, glass, iron & steel, metal, plastic, soap, flower, rubber, candle wax, kitchen waste, and garden waste. Separation of solid waste requires more consistent awareness from all associates at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. Trash bins in public areas are also equipped with signs for sorting waste according to the type of waste. Not only awareness from associates is needed, but also awareness from all guests staying overnight and guests around the Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran hotel to dispose waste according to its type in the trash bins provided by the Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran hotel. Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran also has a composting site. Organic waste will be recycled into compost which is useful for fertilizing plants around the hotel. Composting process conducted in the back area of the hotel and also, Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran have cooperated with third parties which is PT. Jimbaran Lestari that managed all of the waste includes organic waste as compost. Currently, the composting plant at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran is still being used but it is not effective because lack of human resources. Usually, the compost is made directly by the garden staff. This shows that Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran has an awareness to always maintain and preserve the environment. To analyse how the implementation of green purchasing in improving environmental awareness at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran, it can be seen from several indicators of the implementation of Green Purchasing which have a relationship with the Environmental Awareness indicator bellow:

Figure 2. Relationship of Indicator

Refer to the Figure 2, it can be seen that the assessment based on quality management system and supplier ISO certification is related to recognizing environmental issues. The aim of assessing product’s quality management system from the supplier in providing kitchen’s goods is to evaluate and ensure that the kitchen’s goods obtained are in accordance with the quality standards of Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran without having a negative impact to the environment. The other indicator is selecting suppliers that have been certified ISO. The credibility of a company that compete in global range could be measured by this ISO standard. By selecting the certified suppliers, hotel could get a guarantee that the production activities by these suppliers will not have negative impact to the environment. This shows that if the green. Purchasing indicator has been implemented, it will help the purchasing section in recognize environmental issues in the process of procuring goods and also by assessing materials based on a quality management system and combined with choosing ISO certified suppliers. This will provide knowledge to the purchasing section in understanding and recognizing various environmental issues to maximize the potential of suppliers with these criteria. One of the suppliers that has cooperated with Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran is Yumico, where Yumico already has ISO22000 certification. It can be concluded that the implementation of green purchasing will help improving environmental awareness by having knowledge in understanding various environmental issues with assessment based on quality management system from certified ISO suppliers at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran.

The third indicator is eco-labelling of products, which stated that it is related to environmental knowledge dimension namely recognizing environmentally friendly products. The application of eco-labelling of products will help the purchasing section to be able to recognize environmentally friendly products during the procurement process which can be seen directly from the product labels that are usually listed on the special packaging of various kitchen’s goods at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran. By the implementation of eco-labelling of products, it will be able in improving the purchasing section's knowledge in recognizing products that are safe to use with degradable materials, recyclable and environmentally friendly. It will also improve the awareness of the purchasing section to be able to develop products that are environmentally friendly by being able to use various products that have

eco labelling so that they can improving environmental awareness. It can be concluded that the implementation of green purchasing will help in improving environmental awareness at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran.

Fourth indicator is implementing Health, Safety, and Environment (HSE) system, that it is related to understanding consequences of product purchases. By implementing the HSE system, all kitchen's goods purchased are guaranteed not to have a significant impact to the environment. When purchase the kitchen's goods, it is required to considering the consequences of the items based on the HSE system. (1) Health is where the goods purchased are safe to use, it does not contain hazardous materials and not dangerous for human health, (2) Safety is where the product is not processed by over-exploiting resources until the procuring process of the goods to the hotel is ensured to be safe, (3) Environmental system is whether the product can be recycled or not. The implementation of green purchasing indicators from the supplier selection dimension will help the purchasing section have the knowledge to understand the impact or consequences of purchasing a product to the environment. It can be concluded that the implementation of green purchasing in this indicator will help in improving environmental awareness by understanding the impact or consequences of purchasing goods through the importance of implementing the Health, Safety and Environment System (HSE) at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran.

Fifth indicator is supplier internal management audit that is related to evaluate impact of products purchases. The implementation of supplier internal management audits is carried out routinely by the purchasing section to determine the performance of the items purchased. Currently, supplier internal management audit is not regularly implemented due to limited human resources and time to carry out audits to supplier production sites. The performance of purchasing these kitchen's goods will ensure that they are safe for use and hygiene. This is related to the indicator of environmental awareness on the environmental attitude dimension. Should the implementation of the green purchasing indicator is implemented, it will be able in improving environmental awareness through the attitude of the purchasing section in evaluating environmental performance on the impact caused by kitchen's goods purchased and used at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran.

Sixth indicator is collaboration with suppliers to use environmentally friendly packaging, that is related to minimize negative impact of product purchases. This collaboration will able to assist the purchasing section in minimizing the negative impact of the products purchased, especially for kitchen's goods to the environment. By implementing green purchasing to use environmentally friendly packaging from various suppliers who are able to provide this packaging, it will be able in improving purchasing section awareness in minimizing the negative impact of kitchen's goods purchased to the environment. It can be concluded that the implementation of green purchasing will help purchasing section in improving environmental awareness through purchasing attitudes done by the purchasing section at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran.

Seventh indicator is supplier eco-friendly research and development capability that is related to the consistency in purchasing environmentally friendly products. By researching and developing environmentally friendly suppliers, it will influence the attitude of the purchasing section in purchasing environmentally friendly products. Purchasing section will be more consistent in buying environmentally friendly products by researching suppliers who develop environmentally friendly practices. It can be concluded that the implementation of green purchasing will help purchasing section in improving environmental awareness by researching suppliers who develop environmentally friendly practices so that it will influence the attitude of the purchasing section to be more consistent in purchasing environmentally friendly products at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran.

3R's (reduce, reuse and recycle) procurement process dimension has a close relationship with environmental behaviour. Environmental behaviour is the behaviour on how the associates reducing single use materials, reusing the materials by utilizing waste instead of throwing it away, and managing waste by separating solid waste and recycled waste. This initiative is still being carried out and the awareness of all associates at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran needs to be keeping up. Results showed that environmental commitment, environmental consciousness, green lifestyle, and green self-efficacy positively influenced pro-environmental behaviour (Yusliza et al., 2020).

CONCLUSION

Implementation of green purchasing in procurement process of kitchen's goods at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran has not been implemented optimally because of limited suppliers that can provide eco-friendly kitchen's goods because the cost in purchasing eco-friendly goods is quite expensive. Furthermore, there is no regulations or SOP in selecting the supplier in the Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran based on eco-friendly suppliers. In the procurement process, purchasing section make an effort to reduce waste generated

by minimizing single use materials, reusing waste in procurement process by using cardboard and container, and also selecting the organic waste that can recycled as a compost. Implementation of green purchasing in improving environmental awareness shown by the initiatives of purchasing section gradually replace 100% conventional plastic to the materials that can be more easily to decipher. It also requires the awareness of all associates and also guests at Le Meridien Bali Jimbaran to have the knowledge, attitudes and behaviours in improving environmental awareness to minimizing the single-use materials, reusing resources and recycling waste. Thus, the quality of the environment is still maintained, and sustainable so that it is guaranteed for future generations.

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